

Design, Molecular Modeling, Synthesis and Preliminary Evaluation of Hybrid Molecules of Benzothiazole Cross-Linked with Hydroxamic Acid by Certain Linkers as HDAC Inhibitors

Highlights

New hybrid molecules of benzothiazole with hydroxamic acid were successfully synthesized and recorded remarkable and potential anticancer activity against lung cancer cell line A549.